

PICSE: Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe

*Funded under the EU Framework Programme for Research and innovation H2020
- Grant Agreement no: 644014*

Deliverable Title: Platform Progress Report

Submission Due Date: M13 (October 2015)

Actual Submission Date: 27 October 2015

Work Package: WP1 (Management)

Responsible Partner: CERN

Distribution: Public

Nature: Deliverable

Abstract: This report highlights how the online database to which the Task Force and the PICSE Consortium contributed has been exploited. The report also demonstrates the interactive nature of the platform and its impact on and beyond the procurement community on how crucially important it is to alleviate barriers to innovation in the procurement of cloud-based services.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project	
<i>Project acronym:</i>	PICSE
<i>Project full title:</i>	Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe
<i>Project start:</i>	1 October 2014
<i>Project duration:</i>	18 months
<i>Call:</i>	ICT-35-2014: Innovation and Entrepreneurship Support
<i>Grant agreement no.:</i>	644014
Document	
<i>Deliverable number:</i>	D1.1
<i>Deliverable title:</i>	Platform Progress Report
<i>Author(s):</i>	Konstantinos Papangelopoulos
<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	Rachida Amsaghrou, Bob Jones, Sara Garavelli, Damir Savanovic, Carmela Asero
<i>Work package no.:</i>	WP1
<i>Work package title:</i>	
<i>Work package leader:</i>	CERN
<i>Work package participants:</i>	
<i>Distribution:</i>	
<i>Nature:</i>	
<i>Version/Revision:</i>	VX.X
<i>Draft/Final</i>	
<i>Keywords:</i>	

DISCLAIMER

PICSE (644014) is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020. The PICSE Procurers’ Platform will give access to a unique repository of information supporting the move from outright purchase to ‘pay-per-usage’ made possible by the arrival of cloud computing. It builds on the Helix Nebula collaboration between supply and demand of which the three PICSE partners are key members.

This document contains information on PICSE core activities, findings and outcomes and it may also contain contributions from distinguished experts who contribute to PICSE. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation and publication date. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the PICSE consortium and cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission.

CHANGE LOG

Issue	Date	Description	Author/Partner
	14.09.2015	Submission of first draft	CERN (Kostas Papangelopoulos)
	16.09.2015	Input on first draft internally provided at CERN	Rachida Amsaghrou (CERN)
	30.09.2015	Input on impact of case studies and social media provided by Trust-IT and JRC	Sara Garavelli (Trust-IT), Carmela Asero (JRC)
	02.10.2015	Input internally provided at CERN	Rachida Amsaghrou, Bob Jones (CERN)
	09.10.2015	Input on second draft provided by PICSE Consortium members	Sara Garavelli (Trust-IT), Damir Savanovic (CSA), Carmela Asero (JRC)
	22.10.2015	Final input provided at CERN	Rachida Amsaghrou (CERN)

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1. Executive Summary

The establishment of an online platform has been essential to promote PICSE and to carry forward the contribution of the PICSE Task Force. This report highlights the way in which the PICSE online database was built and how it has been exploited. The overall conclusions - taking into account the objectives of the project- drawn are as follows:

- The visibility (approximately 7.000 visits) of the PICSE web platform since the launch of the project in October 2014, combined with its rich and diverse content have contributed to successfully promoting PICSE and its main outcomes.
- The interactive character and impact of the Web platform is indicated by the high visibility of the “PICSE Partner search” section as well as that of the “Report on experiences from the public sector” (*see figure 7*).
- The Cloud Procurement case studies, an important outcome of the PICSE Consortium members efforts, was effectively promoted through the PICSE Web Platform and the exposure of PICSE on social media. It is now available to the Cloud Computing community offering some valuable information on the way barriers to cloud computing organisations can be eliminated.
- The social media PICSE accounts played a complementary role in promoting and increasing the impact of PICSE, as the number of connections on social media and the diversity of the connections (European Commission, Research and Government Institutions etc) attest.
- The relation between PICSE and Helix Nebula benefited both projects: PICSE was successfully promoted making use of the high visibility and number of participants at the Helix Nebula Initiative (General Assemblies, Helix Nebula official site and Facebook group). Similarly, PICSE provided valuable feedback to the advancement of HNI and HNSciCloud, eg through the D2.2 deliverable (research procurement case studies).
- The PICSE Consortium extensive networks were exploited successfully. This can be concluded from the variety of events at which PICSE was promoted, in both the European and the US market, to realise the PICSE Research case studies, etc (*see 3.1 -3.3*).

2. Introduction

Since its official launch in September 2014, the main focus of PICSE has been to capture the best practices for the procurement of cloud services and stimulate innovation within public sector procurement in line with a procurement roadmap. The PICSE Procurers' Platform has given access to a unique repository of information supporting the move from outright purchase to 'pay-per-usage' made possible by the arrival of cloud computing. It has built on the Helix Nebula collaboration between supply and demand of which the three PICSE partners are key members, including the chair of the Helix Nebula Initiative (HNI), CERN.

The project has also been addressing the fragmented landscape of inconsistent technical approaches and disjointed managerial structures, which prevent the delivery of quality cloud computing e-infrastructures. PICSE has been engaging with cloud service providers, their customers and procurement professionals over a crucial period as Europe's Cloud Strategy comes to fruition and several large multinational procurements (including PPIs and PCPs) take place.

The report initially focuses on the PICSE Consortium members and how their network has been exploited to promote PICSE. A presentation of the PICSE Web Platform and its current content follows. A detailed overview as well as statistical figures related to the Web Platform are provided, in order to demonstrate its interactive nature and impact on and beyond the procurement community. For this purpose, special references will be made to the presence of PICSE in social media (complementary to the Web Platform), the PICSE Wizard as well as the Research Procurement Case Studies. Both of them constitute important elements of the platform, as they have helped recognise and deal with the existing barriers to innovation in the procurement of cloud-based services. The closing part of the report presents the events related to PICSE –and their expected impact- that will take place during the second phase of the project.

2.1. Project Objectives

The objective of the first half of the project was to ensure satisfactory project delivery; including establishing the European Procurers' Platform, the PICSE Task Force and dissemination of project results.

The project management goals can be described more specifically as follows:

- Establishing an efficient relationship with the European Commission
- Achieving an effective and timely governance of the project and performance management
- Communicate accurately and effectively the PICSE project results

Concerning the Communication and dissemination part of the project, the objectives set were to:

- Identify and engage key stakeholders
- Establish strategic alliances
- Communicate and promote the main PICSE outcomes and opportunities offered by PCP/PPI actions
- Enhance the outreach and visibility of the project
- Develop a clear PICSE identity

3. PICSE Consortium members and their contribution

The PICSE consortium is composed of three organisations, the European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN), Trust-IT and Cloud Security Alliance (CSA). Their role and contribution to the project is described in the following section.

PICSE Consortium - members	Location	Involvement – contribution to PICSE
CERN	Geneva, Switzerland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploiting events organised by CERN (eg HNI 6th G.A.) to promote PICSE - Establishing connections through projects CERN is involved in (eg. Helix Nebula Initiative) - Representing PICSE in various Cloud Technology related events
Trust-IT		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engaging case studies interviewees (see below) - Engaging PICSE task force experts (Strategic Blue, IDC) - Promoting PICSE early results through EU related projects (International Research newsletter, iSGTW, Cordis etc) - Exploiting Trust-IT events to promote PICSE (Cloudscape event) - PICSE social media accounts management - Presenting PICSE objectives and activities through presentations/speeches given by TRUST-IT in various events from January to June 2015 (see below)
Cloud Security Alliance (CSA)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presenting PICSE objectives and activities through presentations/speeches given by CSA in various events/summits from January to June 2015 (see below)

		<p>- PICSE benefited from the relationship CSA has established with Internet2 , NET+, FedRAMP (helped establish links with US market) and European CIO Association</p>
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Table 1: PICSE Consortium members

3.1. CERN

In addition to its role as Project Coordinator (WP1), CERN has promoted PICSE extensively, through high-level Cloud technology related events and conferences, or by exploiting events organised by CERN in order to disseminate PICSE to the Procurement Community.

PICSE benefited from the presence of CERN at the following events:

A new start for Europe: Opening up to an era of Innovation, (22-23 June 2015): This workshop brought together EC representatives and participants from key research and innovation organisations to discuss EU policies on three interconnected topics: Open Science, the European Research Area and Innovation.

Open standards for ICT procurement: saving while reducing ICT lock-in (12 June 2015, Brussels): This event brought together MSP members, procurement managers, policymakers and ICT suppliers to discuss how to effectively reduce lock-in by using Open Standards. CERN presented the results of the PICSE cloud procurement barriers analysis as well as its tools to support procurers, IT managers and procurement team belonging to public research organisations.

"Open Science and e-Infrastructures" e-IRG Workshop (3 June 2015, Riga, Latvia): the event was held under the auspices of the Latvian EU Presidency of the European Union and focused on Open Science. CERN represented the European Science Cloud as well as PICSE.

Datacloud World Congress (3-4 June 2015, Monaco): CERN represented PICSE by presenting the cloud challenges related to integration, procurement, hybrid cloud and security.

Public Sector World Cloud Forum (12 December 2014, London): The event brought together senior IT government officials with the discussed topics aiming to help public research organisations answer all cloud computing related questions. CERN represented PICSE by actively participating to the debate on how cloud computing changes the way public research organisations work.

3.1.1 Events organised by CERN

The Helix Nebula & PICSE Open Day Event (CERN, 26.06.2015)

PICSE's presence was further asserted during the recent Helix Nebula Open Day Event: *"Helix Nebula Initiative & PICSE: Towards a European Science Cloud"* (link: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/388437/other-view?view=standard>) organised by CERN. A presentation was given by Trust-IT, during which the PICSE Wizard application was introduced to the public.

The Open Day event organised by the Helix Nebula consortium was streamed live on Friday 26 June from 10:30 to 12:30 CET and from 14:00 to 16:30 CET. The webcast reached a maximum of 71 single IP connections, among which 62% came from EU countries, 32% from Switzerland (of which 96% from CERN) and 6% from non-EU countries (India, Turkey, Taiwan).

Lecture: Legal aspects of Joint Pre-Commercial Procurements: from modelling to implementation (CERN, 25.02.2015)

A public lecture on Public Procurement was given at the CERN IT Amphitheatre on 25 February, 2015. The objective of this presentation, given by Trento Rise, was to review strategies and tips in order to help procurers implement and publish a Joint Pre-Commercial Procurement tender.

The event was streamed online from 14.00 to 15.00 with 70 IP connections, 57% of which from EU countries, 34% from Switzerland (of which 97% from CERN) and 8% from non-EU countries (Russia, Canada, Taiwan, Brasil).

Webinar: Commercial trading of IaaS cloud resources (CERN, 04.12.2014)

Dr. Johannes Watzl and Daniel Hagemeier (Deutsche Börse Cloud Exchange AG) presented the exchange market that DCBE has launched for IaaS cloud resources. The presentation focused on the general concept, the services and the definition of the tradable products, as well as the key elements of neutrality and transparency.

The event was streamed online from 11.00 to 12.00 with a total of 52 connections, 65% of which came from EU countries and 35% from Switzerland (of which 95% from CERN)

Figure 1: CERN contribution to promoting PICSE

3.2 Trust-IT

Trust-IT has been working very closely with small and large enterprises, government and research organisations to drive forward new ideas, pinpoint market opportunities, create multi-stakeholder partnerships and international networks. This background and network of contacts has been exploited by Trust-IT to maximise the stakeholder engagement in PICSE and to spread the results of the project as follows:

Engaging case studies interviewees: the ESA and ECMWF interviews for the case studies were facilitated by the existing contacts established by Trust-IT & CERN within the Helix Nebula Initiative; the FAO case study is the result of a consolidated collaboration that Trust-IT had with FAO within the iMarine initiative in the recent past; the IRSTEA, UCL, ZBW case studies are the fruit of the relations established by Trust-IT through the RDA Europe project, the European plug-in to RDA that Trust-IT is currently coordinating.

Engaging PICSE task force experts: two of the four task force experts (James Mitchell, StrategicBlue & Martin Cunning, IDC) belong to the Trust-IT network of contacts. Trust-IT has fruitful collaborations with both of them in other projects.

Promoting PICSE early results: the most relevant news related to PICSE results have been promoted through the relevant European projects in which Trust-IT is involved (in particular on the RDA and Cloudwatch websites) and through the media contacts that Trust-IT has developed over the years (e.g. International Research newsletter, iSGTW, Cordis, etc.)

Exploiting Trust-IT events to promote PICSE: Since 2009 Trust-IT organises the Cloudscape (cloudscapeseries.eu) self-sustained event. Cloudscape attracts top-level experts from across the globe, offering insights into current and future directions of ICT technology.

PICSE also benefited from the presence of Trust-IT at the following events:

ICT Proposers' Day 2014, 9 October 2014, Florence, Italy: This event brought together policymakers, European projects and organisations to discuss how the new procurement instruments made available by the Commission (PCP and PPI) can contribute to the economic growth of Europe.

Modernizing the public sector and boosting economic growth through Innovation Procurement, 26-27 November 2014, Milan, Italy: The event was a great opportunity for PICSE to establish synergies with players belonging to the Public Administration.

Open standards for ICT Procurement: Sharing of best practices, 3 December 2014, Brussels: this event brought together procurement managers, policy makers and ICT suppliers to discuss how to effectively reduce lock-in by using Open Standards. Trust-IT presented the early results of PICSE.

THINK Cloud Vendors - London, UK, 9 December 2014: The event focused on providing to the audience, mainly UK cloud providers and representatives of the UK government, a better understanding of the opportunities available across the G-Cloud Platform and Digital Marketplace, highlighting the challenges faced and promoting effective strategies for the supplier community when selling cloud services to the Public Sector. The event was an opportunity for PICSE to establish contacts with some potential case studies.

PICSE at the Europeana Tech conference 2015, 13 February 2015, Paris, France: The Europeana Tech conference was attended by over 100 representatives from research institutes and funding agencies. The PICSE presentation was key to engage in the project new case studies and to promote the PCP and PPI instruments.

Figure 2: Trust-IT network and contribution to case studies

3.3 Cloud Security Alliance (CSA)

Over the years, CSA has developed a dense network through its participation in various dissemination activities as well as relations established in both the European and the US market. PICSE has benefited from the strong relations CSA has developed with:

Internet 2 / NET+ : Internet2 is an advanced technology consortium founded by leading USA research universities, and includes more than 400 institutional members. Internet2 has created a program, called NET+, to provide new cloud-based services to higher education institutions through partnerships with commercial providers including infrastructure, platform, software, communications, and security.

US General Services Administration / FedRAMP: FedRAMP is a government-wide program that provides a standardized approach to security assessment, authorization, and continuous monitoring for cloud-based services. FedRAMP uses a “do once, use many times” framework that intends to save costs, time, and staff required to conduct redundant agency security assessments and process monitoring reports. Through its networks, CSA has managed to connect PICSE with the US market, thus bridging Europe and the USA.

European CIO Association: The European CIO Association (EuroCIO) is a European, independent, not-for-profit representative for the large IT-users (demand side of IT), both private and public. With over 600 organizations as members, represented by their highest IT-manager or CIO and representing over 500.000 IT workers, EuroCIO is the largest organization of its kind at the global level, with links to other CIO communities around the world. EuroCIO members share and develop vision and exchange experiences at a European level for the better use of information technology. EuroCIO represents the larger user communities towards the main IT suppliers as well as European authorities including the European Commission and European Parliament, etc. EuroCIO is a very active participant in many programmes of the European Commission including cloud computing, e-skills and security. EuroCIO is a key member of the community supporting the implementation of the European Cloud Strategy and is actively involved in the EC Selected Industry Groups as well as in the European Cloud Partnership Steering Board.

Dissemination Activity	Location	Date	Type	Involved Partners	Value for PICSE
PICSE objectives and activities were presented by partner CSA in a presentation at the ESRT Event.	Brussels, Belgium	January, 2015	Presentation, Panel (approx. 50 attendees from EU bodies, public organisations and IT industry)	CSA	During this event organized by AFCEA (http://www.afcea.org/europe/html/Europea_nCloud-Foreword.asp), CSA presented the topic of PICSE objectives and procurement barriers in order to create awareness of public sector and policy makers.

PICSE objectives and activities were presented by partner CSA in a keynote speech at the CSA Summit during RSA event.	San Francisco, USA	February, 2015	Presentation, Booth (1000+ attendees from US IT Security institutions, US and European IT industry, various academic institutions)	CSA	During the biggest security event organized by RSA (link), CSA presented the topic of procurement barriers and PICSE objectives to achieve procurement best practices in order to create awareness for global security community.
PICSE objectives and activities were presented by partner CSA in a workshop at the InfoSecurity Europe Event.	London, UK	June, 2015	Workshop, Booth (approx. 50 attendees, among which IT providers, public cybersecurity agencies etc)	CSA	The workshop (link) was related to PICSE procurement barriers and best practices and their relationship to SLAs and PLAs in order to create awareness for security community that may not be experts on procurement topics.

Table 2: CSA contribution and dissemination activities

Figure 3: CSA network and contribution to PICSE

4. The PICSE Web Platform

Officially launched in November 2014, the PICSE web platform (www.picse.eu) is the main tool through which the project is promoted to the procurement community. Throughout its lifetime, the platform grew as an increasing number of procurement best practices, barriers, success stories etc. were collected and became available online.

Figure 4: the PICSE online Platform (www.picse.eu)

The following table provides an overview of the platform and how its content developed from the day it was launched:

Section	Sub-menu	Content (general)	Current Content	
Home Page		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PICSE pay-off on the top to describe the project in few lines • PICSE scrolling news • Buttons dedicated to the PICSE Partner Search and the Online Survey • PICSE major stakeholders: the sections explain the benefits for the stakeholders and how they can be part of PICSE • Central section dedicated to PICSE & Helix Nebula • Latest Tweets • Events 	Same as in "Content" and regularly updated	
About PICSE	About PICSE	Overview of the project, objectives, consortium	Same as in "Content" and regularly updated	
	Who is involved	Partner description	Same as in "Content" and regularly updated	
	PICSE Roadmap	Description of the main result of the PICSE project.	Same as in "Content" and regularly updated	
	PICSE Task Force	Description of the PICSE Task Force and its members.	Same as in "Content" and regularly updated	
	PICSE & Helix Nebula	Description of the relation between PICSE and Helix Nebula	Same as in "Content" and regularly updated	
	Communication Kit	Section containing the promotional material developed by the project (flier, poster, etc.).	PICSE Flier, November 2014	
PICSE Partner Search		Section in which cloud providers, public organizations, SMEs and all the actors interested in the ICT8 and ICT36 (focus on cloud) calls can describe their needs, the partners they are looking for the next calls etc. This section facilitates in dialogue between these interlocutors. Users can post their content (the posts are moderated by PICSE consortium to ensure a high quality service) and leave comments.	6 calls, among which: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 ICT8a (PCP) - 2 ICT36 (with focus on Cloud) - 2 ICT 8b 	
Learn about...	Cloud Marketplaces	Cloud marketplaces for science and IaaS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Helix Nebula Marketplace (http://hnx.helix-nebula.eu/) - A Cloud marketplace for IaaS: Deutsche Borse Cloud Exchange (https://cloud.exchange/en/) 	
	Public sector trends to procure Cloud services	Public sector initiatives/actions on Cloud services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - G-Cloud: An interactive framework for the UK Government (https://www.gov.uk/digital-marketplace) - Cloud for Europe: PCP of research and development on cloud computing Services 	
	PCP	Series of content pieces and use cases providing information regarding Pre-Commercial Procurement.	- Link and description to the related Webinar (Legal aspects of PCP, 25.02.2015)	
	PCP vs PPI	Series of content pieces providing information regarding the main differences between PCP and PPI.	Explanation of importance, differences and differences between PCP and PPI, related links	
	WP2014-15: ICT8	Series of content pieces providing information regarding the ICT8 Call.	Challenges, scope, expected impact of ICT8 and ICT36 calls	

	WP2014-15: ICT36 (focus on cloud)	Series of content pieces providing information regarding the ICT36 Call (focus on cloud).	
Events	Events	PICSE & Helix Nebula future events.	- ICT2015: PICSE Networking session - CSA Congress EMA
	Past Events	PICSE & Helix Nebula past events.	112 announcements from M2
	Webinars	Announcement of the webinars and main outcomes. This section was published after the first webinar took place and is continuously updated.	3 webinars announced
In the Media	Interviews & Articles	PICSE & Helix Nebula interviews and articles.	11 in total (among which lsgtw, Forbes)
	Videos	PICSE & Helix Nebula videos.	42 videos on HNX, Helix Nebula and Helix Nebula General Assemblies
	PICSE in the Press	PICSE & Helix Nebula Press clippings.	50 announcements/articles in which Helix Nebula is mentioned
	Press Releases	PICSE & Helix Nebula Press releases.	5 Press releases (PICSE and Helix Nebula).
Publications	Deliverables	PICSE & Helix Nebula deliverables.	- D2.1 Research Procurement model - Procuring cloud services today report - D3.1 Procurement Barriers report - MS2 Procurement model interim release
	Documentation	PICSE & Helix Nebula documents and reports	36 documents: statements, reports application forms relevant to PICSE and HN
	Presentations	PICSE & Helix Nebula presentations.	50 presentations (Helix Nebula, CERN/ESA/EMBL flagships, cloud computing etc.)
Cloud Procurement tips and tricks		A list of documents and useful information on Cloud Procurement	12 reports, articles and case studies, among which PICSE Wizard

Table 4: The PICSE Web platform – content

The “*Current content*” column provides some useful information on how the online platform was built and exploited through the lifetime of the PICSE project. Among the platforms’ content, we could also mention:

-The “*News*”, “*Events*” and “*In the media*” sections, which broad content is being constantly updated, providing visitors and interested parties with material on anything related to PICSE, Helix Nebula and Cloud Computing in general.

-The “*PICSE Partner Search*” enhances the interactive character of the platform bringing together cloud providers, public organizations, SMEs and all the actors interested in the ICT8 and ICT36 (focus on cloud) calls. This section also promotes dialogue among interested parties to exchange on their needs, partners search for the next calls etc.

- The “*Learn about*” section includes broader content relevant to the Cloud Community. For example, the Helix Nebula Marketplace and Deutsche Borsche Cloud Exchange, as well as G-Cloud and Cloud for Europe, which have expanded the reach of the Web Platform.

- The *Procurement barriers report D3.1* which, through recognising barriers in Cloud Computing Procurement has provided useful insight on how crucially important it is to alleviate barriers in the procurement of cloud-based services

- *The Procuring Cloud Services today report (see 4.3)* , including experiences and lessons learnt from the public sector, challenges in purchasing cloud services, feedback on acknowledging and overcoming barriers.

- *The PICSE Wizard (see 4.2)*, a decision support tool that can guide the procurer via a series of multiple choice questions. It was integrated in the PICSE platform after an initial trial period.

4.1 Web Platform Statistics

The PICSE online platform has had almost 7000 visits ever since it was officially launched in November 2014. The following graphics provide some more detailed information on how the visibility of the site advanced over time.

Since its launch in November 2014, the PICSE online platform has averaged a number of 634 visits per month. As indicated in the graphic, the visibility of the site increased significantly during its lifespan, especially in the periods coinciding with the *Digital Single Market Press Release* (April 2014, Helix Nebula was mentioned) and *the Helix Nebula General Assembly and Open Day Event* (June 24-26 2015), where PICSE and the PICSE communication strategy were presented to the public.

***Session:** a period of time where a unique visitor is actively engaged in the website

Figure 5: PICSE Web platform – sessions over time

As indicated in the figure below, the “PICSE Partner Search” is essentially the most popular page, something which indicates that the PICSE Webpage has served successfully as a platform that promotes dialogue among parties involved in Cloud Computing, in which they can describe their needs and search for partners. Next in visibility was the XaaS webinar announcement page, in which visitors could be informed about the content and register for the Webinar. The high visibility of the recently published “Procuring cloud services” report, finally, indicates how the platform serves successfully towards the dissemination of the experiences and lessons learnt from the respective case studies (also see 4.3.)

No	Page	Views
1	PICSE Home Page	6621
2	PICSE Partner Search	459
3	XaaS cloud model Webinar, 21.01.2015	290
4	Who is involved	269
5	Report on experiences and lessons learnt from the public sector (PICSE D2.2.)	209

Table 4: PICSE website – most viewed pages

4.2 The PICSE Wizard (<http://wiz.picse.eu>)

Although cloud services continue to proliferate and evolve rapidly, institutional procurement processes and policies of many research organisations have not evolved at the same rate. The PICSE Wizard aims to bridging that gap, by helping procurers identify and implement a more flexible and agile procurement model.

The wizard is composed of 2 different tools, which help procurers make a self-assessment and evaluate their procurement procedures:

- a) The cloud procurement model - this is conceived mainly for procurers & IT managers from research institutes that have little or no experience of cloud procurement. On a basis of 8 questions, the tool suggests one cloud procurement model.
- b) The self-assessment tool, which is designed for procurers & IT managers from research organisations in general. On a basis of 5 measurement areas, it helps procurers identify the existing procurement methods they use.

4.2.1 Projected Impact

The PICSE Wizard was first launched during the 3rd Digital European Research Area (ERA) Forum meeting (Brussels, 23 April 2015) and disseminated in the summer of 2015. It will be further promoted through a massive campaign in the next few months with a focus on the following:

- sending individual messages to participants of the 6th Helix Nebula General Assembly, LinkedIn members of the PICSE and Helix Nebula accounts, HNSciCloud members and RDA contacts.
- publication of weekly news that aim to raise the interest of the procurement community

- exploring the possibility of EU Assistance for Innovation Procurement embedding the Wizard in their websites
- Promotion of the tool in upcoming events such as the Euritas Summit, ICT 2015 (October 2015), ICT open standards 2015, the CSA EMEA Congress (November 2015), CloudScape VIII (Brussels, March 2016).

4.3 PICSE Research Procurement Case studies

Within the purpose of alleviating barriers to cloud services procurement, Trust-IT conducted a series of case studies (deliverable D2.2.) focusing on the experience of a number of public sector organisations which have either carried out a process to procure cloud services, or are considering doing so.

The experiences vary in terms of success and offer insights into how the procurement of cloud services is impacting on their current processes. The research was recently published on the PICSE online platform and attempted to address questions such as:

- What are the main challenges public organisations face when purchasing cloud services?
- Are organisations able to apply or adapt existing standard procurement policies in order to benefit from what cloud service providers offer?
- Does their staff have the necessary skill-sets to assess the market and make the right choice?

4.3.1 Impact

Overall, the case studies have had a considerable impact as they helped increase awareness on procurement instruments. The impact of the case studies is indicated by their high outreach, as the high number of views on the PICSE Website (see table 4) and the social media (see table 5) demonstrate. There was also very positive feedback on their usefulness from organisations such as ESA and ECMWF, some of which had no previous experience in procuring cloud services.

Tangible impact was perceptible during the Europeana Tech Conference (Paris, February 2015), where the presentation of the case studies by Trust IT attracted the interest of DG Translation. DG Translation had launched a procurement action in 2010, which eventually failed. They requested that PICSE helps them analyse the cause of their failures. The PICSE consortium and task force provided feedback on the case and advice on the creation of future Cloud tenders. The case studies had a direct impact connected with other tangible results, for instance the decision of Europeana to submit an ICT8 proposal after the presentation of PCP/PPI instruments given by Trust-IT during the conference. This has been a successful step towards raising awareness of innovative procurement instruments (PCP PPI), which is part of the PICSE mandate.

Figure 6: Research Procurement case studies – map

4.4 PICSE on social media

The creation of PICSE accounts on social media sites was based on the logic of establishing additional sub-communities as a source of back links to the main PICSE web platform. Accounts were created on the following social media/professional platforms:

- *LinkedIn*: with a network of 125 connections (among which 9 are related to the European Commission, 11 to academia, 23 to the Helix Nebula Initiative, 7 to governmental organisations), the PICSE LinkedIn account is bringing on board new relevant stakeholders and sending targeted messages as well as disseminating the main project outcomes.

- *Twitter*: a community of 85 followers has been created, where PICSE presence at various events (conferences, workshops etc) is promoted and where there is an effort to boost discussion on topics related to PICSE activities.

The following figure provides an overview of the most popular PICSE related topics on Tweeter:

No	Topic	Impressions
1	Report on experiences and lessons learnt from the public sector (PICSE D2.2.)	849
2	European Science Cloud (article in Horizon magazine)	847
3	Report on experiences and lessons learnt from the public sector (PICSE D2.2.) (2)	787
4	'Procuring cloud services" report	787
7	PICSE Wizard launch announcement	390

Table 5: PICSE on Tweeter – most popular topics

- *Facebook*: the Helix Nebula Facebook page is used to leverage the Facebook community (approximately 500 likes) already built by Helix Nebula and to communicate all the PICSE related activities. The research case studies report (D2.2 - 484 people reached) and the PICSE Wizard (153 people reached) were successfully promoted and enhanced PICSE’s outreach.

- *PICSE Task Force members’ individual accounts*: Noteworthy has been the contribution of the PICSE Task Force members through their individual accounts on Twitter. Indicative of this contribution and its impact are the following examples:

- The promotion of the HNI & PICSE Open Day (26 June 2015), which was retweeted by the account (27,000 followers) of the EU Commissioner on Science, Research and Innovation, thus maximizing the visibility of the event.
- The promotion of the PICSE D2.2. deliverable on research organisations procurement case studies, which achieved more than 2,500 impressions on Twitter (an impression is the delivery of a post/tweet to the Twitter stream of an account and measures the overall exposure on Twitter).

Overall, the active PICSE presence through the PICSE official accounts and the individual contribution of the Task Force members on the above networks is substantially contributing to the overall objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy as they are described on the PICSE Communication Plan Report (engaging key stakeholders, increasing the outreach and visibility of the project etc).

4.5 Events-expected impact during the 2nd phase of the project

During the second phase of the project (M13-M18), a series of events and actions will take place, which are expected to influence the content of the PICSE Web Platform as well as increase the impact of PICSE in the cloud procurement community. More specifically:

- The PICSE Wizard will be further promoted (see 4.2.1.), thus helping cloud technology procurers identify and implement the procurement model that best fits their needs.
- The potential contribution of PICSE to the European Science Cloud will be discussed during the *Helix Nebula Initiative 7th General Assembly (Heidelberg, 19-21 January 2016)*
- PICSE, PICSE Wizard as well as the procurement case studies will be promoted through a series of events, namely:
 - the EGI Community Forum (10-13 November 2016 in Bari, IT),
 - the Cloud Security Alliance EMEA congress (16 November 2015, Geneva)
 - the European CIO annual Conference (2-3 December 2015, Italy)
 - the 7th RDA Plenary meeting (March 2016, Japan)
 - the PICSE final event collocated with CloudScape VIII (8-9 March 2016, Brussels)
 - the e-IRG Workshop (9-10 March 2016, Amsterdam)

A meeting on project management for PICSE with the European Commission will also take place in 8 March, 2016.

5. Methodology

This report was created using qualitative tools. PICSE Consortium members were requested to document their contribution to PICSE (section 2). Also, published documentation on PICSE was analysed (Communication & Dissemination Plan, research case studies, HNsciCloud/PICSE proposal and DoW, PICSE collaboration board meetings minutes).

The presentation and assessment of the PICSE Web Platform was made using the respective table (table 4) taken from the PICSE Communication & Dissemination Plan and adjusting it to its present content (the “Current content” column was added). It was also based on extracting data (number of visitors, visibility etc) using the *Google Analytics* tool. The numbers presented for social media were also analysed.

Finally, the attempt to derive conclusions was primarily based on linking the data available and the analysis of the existing content of the Web Platform with the objectives of PICSE as well as the abstract of the report.

Figure 7: Methology used for PICSE D.1.1